

DIGITAL AGE IN DRUG DEVELOPMENT: A REVIEW OF LATEST INDUSTRY GUIDELINES ON RESEARCH DECENTRALIZATION AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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Abstract: *The clinical trials industry plays a vital role in developing and evaluating new medical treatments, therapies, and interventions. High costs, lengthy processes, and strict regulatory requirements contribute to the burdensome nature of conducting clinical trials. Patient recruitment and retention difficulties and data quality and integrity issues further complicate the process. The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the need for alternative approaches, such as decentralized and remote participation, to overcome traditional barriers in clinical trials. Additionally, using artificial intelligence and machine learning (AI/ML) in drug development presents opportunities to enhance the availability of safe and effective drugs, improve health equity, and enable personalized treatments. Regulatory complexities and the importance of maintaining data reliability and security must be considered when implementing AI/ML solutions. This paper provides an overview of the current settings and challenges of the clinical trials industry based on the latest Food and Drug Agency (FDA) guidance, highlighting the need for innovative solutions and a shift towards decentralized and patient-centric approaches in clinical trial design and execution. Paper concludes by emphasizing the potential benefits of AI/ML in drug development and the*

importance of regulatory compliance and data management through decentralization.

Keywords: *clinical trials, decentralized trials, patient recruitment and retention, data integrity, artificial intelligence, regulatory compliance, digital health technologies.*

DIGITALNO DOBA U RAZVOJU NOVIH LEKOVA: PREGLED NAJNOVIJIH SMERNICA INDUSTRIJE O DECENTRALIZACIJI ISTRAŽIVANJA I VEŠTAČKOJ INTELIGENCIJI

Apstrakt: *Industrija kliničkih ispitivanja igra vitalnu ulogu u razvoju i evaluaciji novih medicinskih tretmana, terapija i intervencija. Visoki troškovi, dugotrajni procesi i strogi regulatorni zahtevi doprinose opterećujućoj prirodi sprovođenja kliničkih ispitivanja. Poteškoće u regrutovanju i zadržavanju pacijenata, zajedno sa problemima kvaliteta i integriteta podataka, dodatno komplikuju proces. Pandemija COVID-19 istakla je potrebu za alternativnim pristupima, kao što je decentralizovano i daljinsko učešće, kako bi se prevazišle tradicionalne barijere u kliničkim ispitivanjima. Pored toga, korišćenje veštačke inteligencije i mašinskog učenja u razvoju lekova predstavlja mogućnosti da se poveća dostupnost bezbednih i efikasnih lekova, poboljša zdravstvena jednakost i omogući personalizovani tretman. Regulatorna složenost i važnost održavanja pouzdanosti i sigurnosti podataka moraju se uzeti u obzir prilikom implementacije rešenja veštačke inteligencije. Ovaj rad daje pregled trenutnih postavki i izazova industrije kliničkih ispitivanja, baziranih na najnovijim vodičima Agencije za hranu i lekove iz SAD (FDA), naglašavajući potrebu za inovativnim rešenjima i pomeranjem ka decentralizovanim pristupima usredsređenim na pacijenta u dizajnu i izvođenju kliničkih ispitivanja. U radu se zaključuje sa potencijalnim prednostima veštačke itneligencije u razvoju lekova i važnosti usklađenosti sa propisima i upravljanja podacima kroz decentralizaciju.*

Ključne reči: *klinička ispitivanja, decentralizovana ispitivanja, regrutovanje i zadržavanje pacijenata, veštačka inteligencija, usklađenost sa propisima, digitalne zdravstvene tehnologije.*

INTRODUCTION

The clinical trials industry is crucial in developing and evaluating new medical treatments, therapies, and interventions. It serves as a vital bridge

between scientific research and the availability of safe and effective treatments for patients. However, the industry faces several challenges that impact its efficiency and effectiveness. One significant challenge is the high cost and time-intensive nature of clinical trials. According to a study published in the Journal of Health Economics, the average cost of bringing a new drug to market exceeds \$2.5 billion. [1] The lengthy process of conducting trials, obtaining regulatory approvals, and ensuring patient safety adds to the overall time and financial burden. Another challenge is patient recruitment and retention. Clinical trials heavily rely on recruiting sufficient eligible participants within a specific timeframe. However, recruitment difficulties often arise due to strict eligibility criteria, limited awareness among potential participants, and patient reluctance to participate in experimental treatments. Retaining participants throughout the trial duration is equally essential. However, it can be challenging due to various factors such as treatment burden, adverse events, and participant dropouts. [2] Ensuring data quality and integrity is a critical challenge in the clinical trials industry. Data management, including accurate data collection, analysis, and reporting, is essential for drawing valid conclusions and making informed decisions. However, inconsistencies, missing data, and errors can occur, potentially compromising the reliability and validity of trial results. Maintaining data integrity requires robust systems and processes, adherence to regulatory guidelines, and effective monitoring and auditing. Regulatory compliance is another significant aspect of clinical trials. Strict regulatory requirements are in place to ensure participant safety, ethical conduct, and the validity of trial results. Compliance with complex regulatory frameworks, such as Good Clinical Practice (GCP) guidelines, can be challenging, especially for multinational trials across different jurisdictions. Non-compliance can lead to delays, penalties, and even the termination of trials.

Traditional clinical trial settings often require participants to visit physical trial sites, which can be inconvenient and burdensome, particularly for individuals with limited mobility or those residing in remote areas. The COVID-19 pandemic has further emphasized the need for alternative approaches that reduce the reliance on in-person visits and enable remote participation. [3] Data management and integration pose challenges in clinical trials. With the growing use of digital health technologies and decentralized trial models, diverse data sources need to be collected, stored, and analyzed efficiently while maintaining data security and privacy. [4] Finally, regulatory complexities and compliance requirements present

significant challenges in conducting clinical trials. Researchers and sponsors must navigate a complex web of regulations, guidelines, and ethical considerations to ensure adherence to standards and protect the rights and safety of participants. [5]

Addressing these challenges requires innovative solutions and a shift towards decentralized and patient-centric approaches in clinical trial design and execution. Embracing digital health technologies, optimizing recruitment strategies, streamlining data management processes, and fostering collaboration among stakeholders can contribute to overcoming these obstacles and advancing clinical research.

In this research, we have presented important considerations related to the newest regulatory approaches of the Food and Drug Agency, USA, issued in May 2023 in addition to previous complementary research for conducting clinical trials in digital settings using A.I. and how the diversity in clinical trials should be approached in the latest industry settings.

This is important landscape for global industry development and regulatory views on digital technologies as FDA is leading global institution and clinical research are very sophisticated and innovative industry. Having this said, we can expect in future that all other industries might take over those considerations, adopt for specific industry and develop them further to achieve industry technological brake through. Therefore, attention to this review would be required whether we are involved in drug development processes or in any other industry.

INDUSTRY BACKGROUND

To fulfil its mission of protecting, promoting, and advancing public health, the Food and Drug Administration's (FDA's) Center for Drug Evaluation and Research (CDER), in collaboration with the Center for Biologics Evaluation and Research (CBER) and the Center for Devices and Radiological Health (CDRH), including the Digital Health Center of Excellence (DHCoE), published guide to facilitate a discussion with stakeholders on the use of artificial intelligence (A.I.) and machine learning (ML) in drugs development, including medical devices used with drugs, to inform the regulatory landscape in this area. [6] FDA ensures drug safety and effectiveness while encouraging innovation. [7] Recent technological advancements in data collection and generation, information management, and computing can transform drug development. This ecosystem presents

unique opportunities and challenges, and FDA collaborates with domestic and international partners to maximize the benefits of these innovations.[1] Stakeholders, including developers, manufacturers, regulators, and academic groups, are working together to understand the applications of AI/ML in drug development.[1] By definition, A.I. is a branch of computer science that utilizes algorithms to perform tasks, while ML is a subset of A.I. that develops models through data analysis. [1]

AI/ML can enhance drug development by expediting safe and effective drug availability, improving health equity, enhancing manufacturing quality, ensuring drug safety, and enabling personalized treatment. The discussion paper acknowledges that it is not FDA guidance or policy but rather an opportunity for stakeholders, including researchers and technology developers, to learn and discuss the utilization of AI/ML in drug development. It provides an initial understanding of the considerations involved, including familiarity with FDA activities and regulations. The paper also explores considerations for responsible AI/ML utilization in drug development, highlighting efforts to establish general principles and standards. Considering the diverse nature of AI/ML applications, a risk-based approach is advocated to facilitate innovation and protect public health. The ongoing engagement between FDA and stakeholders aims to establish a shared understanding of rapidly evolving AI/ML systems and their potential in drug development. AI/ML finds applications in various phases of drug development, from drug discovery to postmarket safety surveillance and manufacturing. These applications are not exhaustive, and FDA oversight may or may not be applicable in specific cases.

INDUSTRY SETTINGS FOR A.I. / MACHINE LEARNING USE

The early stages of drug development generally rely on identifying a suitable biological target for drug candidates. AI/ML can be utilized to analyze and synthesize important information from existing scientific research and other data sources to inform biological target selection. AI/ML approaches can mine and analyze complex datasets to predict the structure and function of biological targets, helping in understanding their role in disease pathways[8][9][10]. However, subsequent studies are necessary to validate the role of the identified targets. [1]

The discovery of potential drug candidates involves screening compound libraries and refining compounds' specificity and selectivity for biological targets. AI/ML can predict chemical properties, bioactivity, efficacy, and

potential adverse events of compounds, aiding in compound screening and design. [11] AI/ML can also assist in predicting drug-target interactions, potentially guiding drug repurposing efforts and *de novo* drug design. [12] Furthermore, the availability of real-world data (RWD) from various sources enables AI/ML to identify previously unknown effects of drugs on disease pathways.

Nonclinical research involves *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies to advance potential therapeutics. AI/ML, including computational modelling and simulation techniques, can be applied to analyze data from pharmacokinetic, pharmacodynamic, and toxicologic studies, explore mechanistic models, and

develop predictive models. [13] Physiologically-based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) and physiologically-based PK/PD (PBPK-PD) modelling, along with novel AI/ML algorithms, are being explored for nonclinical applications, potentially improving accuracy in complex data analysis. [14]

AI/ML plays a significant role in streamlining and advancing clinical research. It can assist in patient recruitment, stratification, monitoring, and predicting treatment responses and adverse events. AI/ML algorithms can also analyze electronic health records (EHRs) and other patient data sources to identify relevant cohorts and extract valuable insights. AI/ML's potential to optimize clinical trial design and conduct promises to improve efficiency and patient outcomes in drug development. For example, AI/ML is being utilized to analyze vast amounts of data from both interventional studies (also referred to as clinical trials) and non-interventional studies (also referred to as observational studies) to make inferences regarding the safety and effectiveness of drugs. Additionally, AI/ML has the potential to inform the design and efficiency of non-traditional trials, such as decentralized clinical trials and trials incorporating the use of real-world data (RWD) extracted from electronic health records (EHRs), medical claims, or other data sources. AI/ML may also have a role in analyzing and interpreting data collected from digital health technologies (DHTs) used in clinical studies. Finally, AI/ML could also be used to improve the conduct of clinical trials and increase operational efficiency. The following subsections will highlight some of the uses and potential uses of AI/ML during the design and conduct of clinical research.

AI/ML is increasingly being developed and used to connect individuals to trials for investigational treatments from which participants may benefit. Specifically, AI/ML is being used to mine vast amounts of data, such as data from clinical trial databases, trial announcements, social media, medical literature, registries, and structured and unstructured data in EHRs, which can be used to match individuals to trials. [15] While these algorithms are trained on high volumes of patient data and enrolment criteria from past trials, it is essential to ensure adequate representation of populations that are likely to use the drug (e.g., gender, race, and ethnicity) as matching algorithms are created and, when used, to confirm that equitable inclusion was achieved during the recruitment process. In the future, if properly validated, these technologies may continue to play an increasing role in matching individuals with investigational treatments.

Enrichment strategies can aid participant selection in clinical investigations designed to demonstrate the effectiveness of drug and biological products.

AI/ML has been explored and used as part of a clinical investigation in the prediction of an individual participant's clinical outcome based on baseline characteristics (e.g., demographic information, clinical data, vital signs, labs, medical imaging data, and genomic data). [16] Such predictive models can be used to enrich clinical trials (e.g., identifying high-risk participants or participants more likely to respond to the treatment). When these types of AI/ML algorithms are used for patient evaluation and selection before randomization, it may be possible to reduce variability and increase study power. [17]

In addition to utilization in enrichment strategies, such predictive models can also be used for participant stratification, for example, if an AI/ML model could predict the probability of a serious adverse event before an investigational treatment is administered. Then, based on their predicted risk for these serious adverse events, participants can be stratified into different groups and then monitored accordingly (or excluded depending on the predicted severity of the adverse event).

AI/ML can characterize and predict pharmacokinetic (P.K.) profiles after drug administration. Considering confounding factors, it can also be used to study the relationship between drug exposure and response. These kinds of models can be used to optimize the dose/dosing regimen selection for a study. [18] AI/ML can be utilized to analyze the large and diverse data generated from continuously monitoring persons using these technologies. This could include using AI/ML to aid in the evaluation of multimodal data and composite measures that may combine individual measures collected through multiple digital health technologies (DHTs). [19] AI/ML can be used for a range of data cleaning and curation purposes, including duplicate participant detection and imputation of missing data values, as well as the ability to harmonize controlled terminology across drug development programs. [20] Use of AI/ML could also significantly enhance data integration efforts by using supervised and unsupervised learning to help integrate data submitted in various formats and perform data quality assessments. Additionally, AI/ML can be used for data curation via masking and de-identifying personally identifiable information, creating metadata, and searching and retrieving stored data. These applications can increase data accuracy and improve the speed at which data are prepared for analysis. AI/ML has been used to analyze high volumes of diverse and complex real-world data (RWD) extracted from electronic health records (EHRs), medical claims, and disease registries, among other sources. Additionally, the use of AI/ML in predictive modelling and counterfactual simulation to inform

clinical trial designs is being actively explored. For example, *in silico* clinical trials utilize computational modelling and simulation to evaluate drug candidates using a virtual cohort of simulated participants with realistic variability of traits representing the desired participant population. [21] AI/ML could be employed in these situations to aid in evaluating a vast number of counterfactual simulations and to predict trial outcomes before human trials. At an even more personalized level, AI/ML can also be used in the context of digital twins of patients, an emerging method that could potentially be used in clinical research. To create digital twins of patients, AI/ML can be utilized to build *in silico* representations or replicas of an individual that can dynamically reflect molecular and physiological status over time. [22] Compared to a participant in a clinical trial that received an investigational treatment, the digital twin could potentially provide a comprehensive, longitudinal, and computationally generated clinical record that describes what may have happened to that specific participant if they had received a placebo.

DECENTRALIZATION IN DIGITALIZED CLINICAL RESEARCH

In the following text, we will present views of the FDA on several major topics, such as Decentralized Clinical Trial (DCT), which represent a clinical trial where trial-related activities occur at locations other than traditional clinical trial sites; Digital Health Technology (DHT), representing a system utilizing computing platforms, connectivity, software, and sensors for healthcare and related purposes. DHT technologies encompass various applications, from general wellness to medical device use. They include technologies designed for medical product use and those used in conjunction with other medical products (devices, drugs, and biologics). DHTs may also be employed in the development and study of medical products. In addition to this, Investigational Product (I.P.) refers to human drugs, biological products, or devices that are undergoing investigation in a clinical trial, and telehealth represents the utilization of electronic information and telecommunications technologies to support and facilitate long-distance clinical healthcare. [23]

In fully decentralized clinical trials, trial activities occur at locations other than traditional trial sites, such as participants' homes or local healthcare facilities. Decentralized hybrid trials combine in-person visits to traditional trial sites with activities conducted at non-traditional locations. The FDA's

regulatory requirements for investigations of medical products are the same for decentralized clinical trials (DCTs) and traditional site-based trials.

Clinical trials already include decentralized elements where certain activities involving participants occur outside traditional trial sites. For instance, laboratory tests are often conducted at remote clinical laboratory facilities. DCTs can improve access to diverse patient populations and enhance trial efficiencies. Advances in telehealth and digital health technologies allow for fewer in-person visits and the collection of trial-related data remotely. This convenience benefits participants, reduces caregiver burden, and facilitates research on rare diseases and populations with limited mobility or access to traditional trial sites. Decentralized trials can enhance a diverse clinical population's engagement, recruitment, enrolment, and retention. Fully decentralized trials are suitable for investigational products that are easy to administer, have well-characterized safety profiles, and do not require complex medical assessments. Hybrid decentralized trials are more appropriate when specific assessments or I.P. administration need to occur at a clinical trial site, while others can be conducted remotely.

Challenges associated with DCTs include coordinating trial activities across multiple non-traditional locations. DCTs require specific plans to facilitate decentralization, including using local healthcare facilities, healthcare providers, clinical laboratory facilities, home visits, and direct distribution of investigational products to participants at their locations. Appropriate training, oversight, and risk assessment should be in place.

In a DCT, trial-related activities occur at locations other than traditional sites and involve a network of locations. For inspection purposes, there should be a physical location where trial records are accessible, and interviews can be conducted. The variability and precision of data obtained in DCTs may differ from traditional site-based trials, which can impact the validity of non-inferiority findings. Remote assessments may introduce variability, including those performed by trial participants or local healthcare providers. Calculating non-inferiority margins in DCTs may pose challenges, and FDA review divisions should be consulted in planning non-inferiority trials in a DCT setting.

In-person visits and trial-related activities can be conducted by trial personnel who are sent to participants' homes or preferred locations. [24] Depending on the trial protocol, in-person visits and trial-related activities may also be conducted by healthcare providers (HCPs) who are located close to trial participants' homes but are not part of the trial

personnel. These local HCPs, such as doctors or nurses, may be used by sponsors or investigators to perform trial-related activities fee-for-service. The trial-related services they provide should align with their qualifications in clinical practice, such as performing physical examinations, reading radiographs, and obtaining vital signs, without requiring detailed knowledge of the trial protocol or investigational product (I.P.). [25]

However, trial-related activities that are unique to research and require detailed knowledge of the protocol or the I.P. should be performed by qualified trial personnel who have received appropriate training. Both trial personnel and trial participants, when applicable, should be trained on how to conduct or participate in a telehealth visit. During each remote trial visit, investigators should confirm the participant's identity. The FDA does not endorse any specific identification method, but sponsors and investigators can refer to existing digital identity guidelines. [26]

Case report forms and other documentation should be completed for telehealth visits, including recording the visit's date, time, and location. [27] The trial protocol should specify how remotely identified adverse events will be evaluated and managed. Additionally, it is the responsibility of the sponsor and investigator to ensure that remote clinical trial visits conducted via telehealth comply with the relevant laws governing telehealth in the applicable U.S. states or territories and other countries. [27]

Digital Health Technologies (DHTs) enable remote data transmission from trial participants regardless of location.[27] Sponsors should consider the guidance provided by the FDA on using DHTs in clinical investigations, which includes recommendations for selecting and validating DHTs, collecting data remotely, training on their use, and managing risks associated with their use in clinical trials.

The roles and responsibilities of sponsors and investigators in DCTs are related to ensuring proper coordination of decentralized activities and strive for diversity and inclusiveness in trial populations. They can utilize local healthcare institutions for outreach and consider bringing trial-related activities to participants' homes through DHTs to improve engagement, recruitment, and retention, particularly for individuals facing challenges accessing traditional clinical trial sites. The use of local HCPs close to potential participants' homes can also enhance the engagement and recruitment of diverse participants while reducing cultural or linguistic barriers to participation [27].

Sponsors must include a data management plan (DMP) in the trial protocol, specifying data origin, flow, and acquisition methods from various sources. The DMP should identify vendors for data collection, handling, and management. Operational aspects of the DCT, such as scheduled and unscheduled clinical trial visits, transmission of reports, delivery of investigational products, safety monitoring, and management of adverse events, should be described in the trial protocol. Case report forms should include information about when and where data were collected and by whom. Sponsors must comply with relevant local laws, regulations, and licensing requirements regarding medical practice and I.P. administration during DCTs. Proper investigation monitoring should also be ensured, employing risk-based approaches based on the sponsor's assessment [27].

SOFTWARE USED IN CONDUCTING DIVERSIFIED CLINICAL TRIALS (DCTs)

Software programs used to produce and process trial records are subject to 21 CFR part 11, which sets forth the requirements for electronic records and electronic signatures in the United States. [28] These programs must ensure data reliability, security, privacy, and confidentiality. The FDA's regulations on electronic records and signatures aim to ensure the integrity and trustworthiness of electronic data in clinical trials. Compliance with 21 CFR part 11 is crucial for maintaining data integrity and meeting regulatory standards. [29] The FDA considers real-time video interactions, telehealth, and live information exchanges between trial personnel and participants. As such, they are not considered electronic records and are not subject to 21 CFR part 11. However, local laws governing telehealth may apply. Privacy and security should be ensured during real-time visits, which must be appropriately documented. Suppose this documentation is captured in electronic form. In that case, it is subject to 21 CFR part 11. [30] When using software solutions, clinical research sponsors should consider the following aspects concerning software implemented in decentralized clinical trials (DCTs). The software used to support DCT operations can be executed on various platforms, such as tablets, cell phones, and personal computers. It serves multiple functions, including managing electronic informed consent, capturing and storing reports, managing electronic case report forms (eCRFs), scheduling trial visits, tracking investigational products (I.P.s), syncing information recorded by digital health technologies (DHTs), and serving as communication tools between DCT personnel and trial participants. [31]

CONCLUSION

The clinical trials industry is critical in advancing medical treatments and therapies, but it faces various challenges that impact its efficiency and effectiveness. The high cost and time-intensive nature of conducting trials, patient recruitment and retention difficulties, data quality and integrity issues, and regulatory compliance complexities are among the significant challenges faced by the industry. These challenges hinder the timely availability of safe and effective patient treatments and necessitate innovative solutions.

The COVID-19 pandemic has underlined the need for alternative approaches in clinical trials, such as decentralized and remote participation, to overcome traditional barriers. Digital health technologies and decentralized trial models offer opportunities to reduce the reliance on in-person visits, improve participant engagement, and collect diverse data sources more efficiently while ensuring data security and privacy. However, navigating the regulatory landscape and ensuring compliance with complex frameworks remain critical considerations for researchers and sponsors.

Artificial intelligence and machine learning (AI/ML) in drug development holds excellent potential for expediting the availability of safe and effective drugs, enhancing health equity, improving manufacturing quality, ensuring drug safety, and enabling personalized treatments. Therefore, the FDA recognizes the opportunities and challenges associated with AI/ML in drug development and actively invites feedback from stakeholders to establish a shared understanding and facilitate responsible utilization.

Furthermore, the FDA acknowledges the importance of software programs in producing and processing trial records, emphasizing compliance with 21 CFR part 11 to ensure data reliability, security, and confidentiality. Real-time video interactions, including telehealth, are considered live information exchanges and are not subject to 21 CFR part 11. However, privacy, security, and appropriate documentation during real-time visits are crucial considerations. Addressing the challenges faced by the clinical trials industry requires embracing innovative approaches, leveraging digital health technologies, streamlining data management processes, ensuring regulatory compliance, and fostering collaboration among stakeholders. By doing so,

the industry can advance the field of clinical research, accelerate the development of new treatments, and improve patient outcomes.

The landscape of global industry development and regulatory views on digital technologies is of significant importance. As a leading global institution, the FDA plays a crucial role in shaping the future of clinical research, which is a highly sophisticated and innovative industry. The advancements and considerations made in this field have far-reaching implications, not only for drug development but also for other industries. It is anticipated that these considerations will serve as a catalyst for technological breakthroughs across various sectors. Therefore, it is imperative to pay attention to these developments, regardless of our involvement in drug development processes. The insights gained from the FDA's efforts can pave the way for innovation and progress in various industries, setting a precedent for the adoption and further development of digital technologies.

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